

AMIR TEMUR - DEFENDER OF HOMELAND AND NATION

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Shamshiev Ravshan Rustam ugli

CHOTKMBYU

lieutenant colonel

Annotation: *This article is about the great Amir Temur. He was an influential person of his time.*

Keywords: *independence, nationality, great, tradition, Amir Temur, state, development.*

INTRODUCTION

Independence is very dear to us, first of all, because it has returned our sacred values, rich cultural and spiritual heritage, including the truth about the personality of the great Amir Temur. That is why in our country the birthday of Amir Temur is widely celebrated annually, and it has become a tradition to hold various events on the ground, including the “Days of Amir Temur”, dedicated to the history of his life and work, understanding the role and significance of Sohirkiron in the history of the Uzbek people. In the era of the totalitarian regime, Amir Temur was considered an "invader and destroyer", his personality was treated without due respect, books and articles were published that caused readers to hate him¹. It is no secret to anyone that only after Uzbekistan achieved state sovereignty, our people got the opportunity to revive respect for the historical merits of Amir Temur. Thanks to independence, we began to understand our past more deeply, and it is through this prism that confidence in our future is formed in us.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Undoubtedly, the study of the life and work of Amir Temur will allow everyone to know the priceless legacy left by Sohirkiron in world history. He played an unprecedented role in the development of the Uzbek statehood. In the history of the peoples of the world, Amir Temur is assessed as a great statesman, a talented commander, and a bright personality. At one time, he not only revived the Uzbek statehood, but raised it to a new level of development, which made him famous throughout the world.

¹ Clavijo G. Travel diary to the palace of Amir Temur in Samarkand (in Uzbek). T., “Uzbekistan”, 2010, 156 p.

A talented literary scholar and writer, author of more than ten monographs and works of art related to the history of Kashkadarya, Karshi, Shakhrisabz, Sohibkiron Amir Temur and the Timurids, Poyon Ravshanov, also cites the following testimony from Ibn Arabshokh²:

“Temur was tall, walked straight like the ancient heroes, he had a wide forehead, a large head, very strong and strong-willed, with a beautiful tall posture, his face was white with red tints, but without spots, he was not swarthy, the arms and legs were powerful, the shoulders were broad, the fingers were full, the calves were powerful, the body was perfect, bearded, the right arm and leg were paralyzed, both eyes sparkled like candles, but did not express joy, the voice was rough ... He did not like jokes and lies, he was indifferent to entertainment, he liked to be betrayed, even if there was something against him in his words.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Amir Temur's youth passed during the height of Mongol despotism. At that time, the Chigatai ulus was renamed into Movaraunnahr (an ulus is a large administrative-territorial division of the feudal state in Central Asia at that time). The Mongols destroyed cities and villages, mosques and cathedral mosques, libraries and irrigation systems. The people suffered from their oppression and deprivation. In addition, in various parts of the region, feuds arose every now and then between local clans advocating sovereignty, in particular, in Khorezm - Sufis, in Kashkadarya - Barlos, in the Akhangaran valley - Zhaloirs, in Bukhara - Sadrs, in Termez - sayyids and other forces, because of which a serious danger of bloodshed arose throughout Movaraunnahr. That is why in 1360 the Khan of Mongolia Tugluk Temur captured Movaraunnahr to teach the local rulers a lesson. At this difficult moment, young Temurbek appeared on the political arena of Movaraunnahr, setting himself a noble goal - to liberate the region from the Mongol invaders. He reasonably assessed the political situation and realized that in order to achieve his goal, he needed to be extremely careful, gather patriotic forces around him, and when the right moment came, launch an offensive against the enemy.

Already in 1371, Amir Temur united all territories and clans striving for independence. The main goal that he pursued in his many years of struggle with the Mongol Emir Kamariddin was to annex the entire eastern part of Movaraunnahr to his state. And this played a decisive role in the restoration of Uzbek statehood and the formation of a centralized state.

² Ibn Arabshoh, History of Amir Temur (in Uzbek), T., Shark, 2012, 65 p.

To annex Khorezm to Movaraunnahr by peaceful means, Amir Temur sent letters to the leaders of the Sufi clan Husayn, Yusuf and Suleiman, who ruled Khorezm, through his ambassadors. However, they did not agree to Amir Temur's fair proposal. Subsequently, he was forced to send his troops to Khorezm 5 times, and only after the last campaign in 1388, Khorezm was annexed to his empire. And before these events, the rulers of Shosh, Termez, Hisor, Badakhshon, Kunduz recognized the rule of Amir Temur and submitted to his will³.

Thus, thanks to many years of military campaigns, the adoption of reasonable measures and the skillful use of diplomatic art, Amir Temur gradually liberated the country from the Mongol yoke, put an end to political strife and internecine conflicts, and laid the foundations of a centralized state.

Amir Temur not only consistently renewed the Uzbek statehood, formed before him, but also made a serious contribution to its further development, ensuring the protection of the rights and interests of various social strata of the population. It was Amir Temur who, for the first time in world history, divided society into 12 strata and determined the appropriate level for each of them, which greatly facilitated the relationship between the state and society.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, historians and writers who studied the era of Amir Temur and his activities, not without reason called him "Sohibkiron of seven worlds", "Conqueror of padishahs and sultans", "Genius of statehood", "Extremely strong ruler" and so on. But no one could determine the historical role and significance of all the activities of Amir Temur more accurately than the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov: "Amir Temur is the personification of the Uzbek people", "Amir Temur's awareness is self-awareness", "Amir Temur is our pride". It is this impartial assessment that reflects the significance of the activity and the whole meaning of the life of Sohobkiron Amir Temur in the history of the Uzbek people.

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